

Valorization of Contaminated *Ficus Carica* Fruit Residues for Biohythane Production by Consolidated Anaerobic Dark Fermentation

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Abstract

The quest for a reliable, eco-friendly, and sustainable alternative energy source has led to the exploration of utilizing inexpensive organic waste as a substrate for biofuel production. This study focuses on the sequential biohydrogen and biomethane productions with the side products of organic acids and solvents from the contaminated fruit of *Ficus carica* through consolidated bioprocessing at mesophilic conditions (37 °C). The research involved the extraction of fermentable sugar from dried fruit of *F. carica* with an average particle diameter of 275 µm at 100 °C for 1 h which results in 45% sugar recovery from 50 g/L fig residue. Consolidated batch dark fermentation was conducted in sealed 310-mL capacity serum bottles with a working volume of 200 mL, containing fig fruit waste at an initial substrate concentration ranging from 10 g/L to 25 g/L. Total gas volume, hydrogen, total sugar, organic acid, and solvent concentrations were monitored daily. Fermentation setup with an initial fruit waste concentration of 10 g/L, corresponding to a sugar concentration of 5 g/L, resulted in high volumetric hydrogen production rate of 110.50 mL/L·day. Acetic and butyric acids were the dominant organic acids determined in all the experimental setup and their concentration increases as fermentation time progressed. Acetone was consistently detected in all setups. Subsequently, in studies of methane production under mesophilic conditions, residual acetic acid from hydrogen production was used and adjusted to three different initial total acetic acid concentrations—1.5, 3, and 6 g/L—with methanogen-containing anaerobic sludge serving as the inoculum. Methane production was observed only at an initial concentration of 1.5 g/L, resulting in a cumulative methane volume of 174 mL. The results underscore consolidated bioprocessing as an effective approach for producing biohydrogen, biomethane, organic acids, and solvents from sugar-rich *F. carica* fruit.

Keywords: Consolidated fermentation, biohydrogen, biomethane, biohythane

Introduction

The increasing demand in the energy sector, coupled with the declining reserves of fossil fuels, necessitates the exploration of new and renewable energy sources. The use of fossil fuels results in greenhouse gas emissions, which lead to a host of environmental problems [1]. Additionally, the disposal of high organic content waste through costly methods causes irreversible environmental damage, with uncontrolled CO₂ emissions significantly contributing to environmental and climate change [1,2]. In this context, biofuels have gained considerable interest as environmentally friendly alternatives. Biohythane, an innovative biofuel produced from organic waste through biological processes, contains both hydrogen and methane gases [3]. This fuel offers a sustainable solution for energy production, reducing reliance on fossil fuels and minimizing environmental impacts. The combination of biohydrogen and biomethane production from organic wastes via anaerobic fermentation can yield a biohythane gas composed of 10-15% H₂, 50-55% CH₄, and 30-40% CO₂ [4]. Biohythane can be further upgraded to biobased hythane by removing CO₂ [4]. This biohythane fuel provides a sustainable solution for energy production, reducing dependence on fossil fuels, minimizing environmental impacts, enhancing energy security, and supporting environmental sustainability.

Methane has been in use as an energy source for years. Mixing H₂ with CH₄ and natural gas improves its fuel properties [5]. Two-stage sequential biohydrogen-biomethane production processes can be used to complete the conversion of biomass into a renewable energy source resulting in an H₂/CH₄ gas mixture without leaving any residual organic pollutants [6,7]. In the two-stage split system, differences in operating and production conditions, rate-limiting biological reactions, and inhibition are more easily controlled for two gaseous biofuel products. For example, the optimal pH range for biohydrogen

generation is 5.0-6.5, while for methane generation, it is 7-8, with the ideal value being pH of 7 [8–10].

Substrates rich in carbohydrates, such as agricultural waste, lignocellulosic waste, household solid waste, kitchen waste, and vegetable and fruit waste, are commonly utilized in fermentation processes for the production of H₂ and CH₄ [4]. Among these substrates, fig fruit waste stands out as an ideal substrate for biohydrogen production due to its nutrient levels, high sugar concentrations, and biodegradability.

Traditionally, organic substrates undergo pretreatment through physical, physicochemical, chemical, or biological approaches to extract fermentable sugars for use by bacteria in subsequent fermentation processes [11]. However, pretreatment can have adverse consequences. For instance, prolonged exposure during physical and mechanical processes may lead to the partial breakdown of sugars, while chemical pretreatment can result in the formation of inhibitors such as hydroxymethylfurfural and 2-furaldehyde [12]. Therefore, consolidated fermentation may provide a solution to these problems. In consolidated fermentation, microorganisms effectively break down complex lignocellulosic materials into simpler sugars, which are then simultaneously fermented into the desired product, eliminating the need for separate pretreatment [13]. This study focuses on the sequential production of biohydrogen and biomethane with the side products of organic acids and solvents from *F. carica* fruit through consolidated bioprocessing at mesophilic conditions (37 °C).

Material and Methods

Sample Collection and Preparation

The waste fig fruits utilized in this study were obtained from the Aegean Exporters Association in Izmir, Türkiye. Initially, the figs were manually reduced to a size of ≤ 3 cm and subsequently dried at 75°C for 72 hours using a JEIOTECH GC 300/1000 oven. Following the drying process, the figs were mechanically ground to further reduce their particle size. The ground figs were then sieved using Retsch AS 200 BASIC sieves at the Mining Engineering Department Laboratories to classify particle sizes. For the experimental studies, a particle size of $D_p \approx 275 \mu\text{m}$ was selected.

Partial Hydrolysis

The ultra-fine powder of fig waste was subjected to boiling at 100°C to achieve partial hydrolysis, facilitating the transfer of easily soluble simple sugars into the liquid phase. During the boiling process, samples were collected at different interval time to measure the total sugar concentration. The sugar recovery rate (% sugar/fig waste, w/w) was calculated. The aim of partial hydrolysis is to supply the minimum carbon source necessary for microbial growth at the start of fermentation, rather than recovering the entire sugar content of the figs. Consequently, a thermal treatment time yielding a sugar recovery rate of 10-20% is considered sufficient for hydrolysis.

Microorganism

The bacterial culture *Clostridium pasteurianum* DSM 525, obtained from the German Collection of Microorganisms and Cell Cultures GmbH, was utilized in this study. To increase the concentration of the bacterial culture prior to fermentation, it was anaerobically fermented at 37°C and pH 7.0 for 24 hours in 1 L bottles. The fermentation medium comprised 40 g/L glucose, 20 g/L CaCO₃, 10 g/L yeast extract, and 0.1 g/L L-cysteine. Gas measurements were conducted to verify the viability of the microorganisms after being incubated for one day before use.

Fermentation

The experimental setup involved conducting consolidated batch dark fermentation processes at 37°C in airtight serum bottles with a capacity of 310 mL. The initial fig substrate concentration ranged from 10 g/L to 25 g/L. Each fermentation batch consisted of 200 mL of fermentation medium, with the remaining volume allocated as gas space. The fermentation medium comprised partially hydrolyzed fig at an initial biomass concentration of 10-25 g/L, 20 g/L CaCO₃, 10 g/L yeast extract, and 0.1 g/L L-cysteine. L-cysteine was added as an oxygen scavenger to maintain anaerobic conditions, and nitrogen gas was passed through the gas phase to purge oxygen. The pH was monitored daily and adjusted to 6.5-7.0 using dilute NaOH. No external nitrogen, phosphorus, or other nutrients were added to the medium. The stock culture volume added to the fermentation medium was 50 mL, constituting 40% of the fermentation reaction liquid volume.

Methane Production

Methane production experiments were conducted using 310 mL serum bottles. During hydrogen production, the residual organic acids in the liquid phase, particularly acetic acid concentrations, were adjusted to various levels. Methane-producing bacteria were introduced by adding treated sludge from the yeast industry, which had undergone thermal treatment. The experiments were carried out at 37°C under batch and static conditions. To ensure anaerobic conditions, L-cystine was incorporated as an oxygen scavenger, and nitrogen gas was used to purge oxygen from the gas phase. The pH of the medium was monitored daily and maintained within the range of 7.0-7.5 by the addition of dilute NaOH.

Analytical Methods

Daily samples were centrifuged at 7000 rpm for 20 minutes. The resulting liquid phase, separated from the solid phase containing microorganisms, was stored at +4°C for subsequent analysis.

Total Sugar Analysis

Total sugar analysis was performed using the phenol-acid method [14], a spectrophotometric technique. For this, 1 mL of the sample, 1 mL of phenol solution, and 5 mL of H₂SO₄ were added to glass tubes and incubated in a water bath at 20-25°C for approximately 20 minutes until the color stabilized. The absorbance values of the samples were measured at a wavelength of 490 nm using a UV-visible spectrophotometer (Varian Cary 50 Bio model) and quartz cuvettes. Control samples were prepared using the same method. The concentration calculations were derived from the calibration curve of absorbance versus concentration.

Hydrogen Analysis

The total gas volume produced was determined using a gas-liquid displacement system based on the principle of communicating vessels. The liquid solution consisted of a mixture of 2% H₂SO₄ and 10% NaCl. Hydrogen gas measurements were performed using an Agilent 6890 (Varian 3600) Gas Chromatograph. The column was Alltech, Hayesep D 80/100 6" x 1/8" x 0.085", with nitrogen (30 mL/min) as the carrier gas. Oven temperature was 35°C, injection temperature 200°C, and filament 140°C. The hydrogen concentration of the total gas taken from the fermentation medium was measured using a gas-tight glass syringe.

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Organic Acid and Solvent Analysis

Acetic acid, propionic acid, butyric acid, ethanol, and acetone concentrations were measured using HPLC (Agilent 1100 Series). The mobile phase was 5 mM H₂SO₄ with a flow rate of 0.6 mL/min. The column was Aminex HPX-87H Ion Exclusion Column 300 mm x 7.8 mm. Organic acid analyses were conducted with diode array detector at 40 °C oven temperature and 210 nm wavelength. Solvent analyses were conducted with refractive index detector at 40 °C temperature.

Results and Discussion

Partial Hydrolysis of Contaminated Fruit of *Ficus carica*

The primary challenge in hydrogen production via consolidated fermentation is the difficulty in releasing fermentable sugars from particulate matter through microbial hydrolysis. This issue can be addressed by employing partial hydrolysis to release fermentable sugars, thereby allowing the organism to maintain its vital functions before applying consolidated fermentation. In this study, partial hydrolysis of fig waste was conducted by boiling 50 g/L of the waste at 100°C, which facilitated the transfer of soluble simple sugars into the liquid phase. During the hydrolysis process, aliquots of the hydrolysate were taken at various time intervals to measure total sugar content, and the duration required to reach a constant concentration was determined. For economic efficiency, a short-term heat treatment of one

hour that results in 45% sugar recovery from 50 g/L fig residue was found to be sufficient, and this protocol was subsequently used for substrate preparation in further experiments.

Hydrogen, Organic Acid, and Solvent Productions under Mesophilic Conditions

In studies of hydrogen gas production under mesophilic conditions, the initial fig concentration was varied between 10 g/L and 25 g/L. The sugar concentrations released from partially hydrolyzed figs were adjusted between 5 g/L and 15 g/L under fermentation conditions. The results based on initial sugar concentration are described below.

Fermentation with an initial fig concentration of 10 g/L, corresponding to a sugar concentration of 5 g/L, resulted in continuous hydrogen production until approximately the 72nd hour, after which it stabilized (Figure 1). The maximum volume of hydrogen produced was 26 mL, achieving a volumetric hydrogen production rate of 110.50 mL/L·day at this biomass concentration. This change in hydrogen production can be attributed to the increase in fermentable sugar concentration, which rose from 5 g/L at the onset of fermentation to 13.09 g/L after 72 hours, facilitated by bacterial hydrolysis of residual sugars in the ground and thermally treated fig particles. Throughout the fermentation period, the organisms remained active in the presence of fermentable sugars, generating organic acids and hydrogen. The organic acid profile, detailed in Table 1, revealed increases in acetic acid concentration from an initial 0.96 g/L to 3.23 g/L. Trace amounts of propionic acid were detected towards the end of fermentation, while lactic acid was absent, and the concentration of butyric acid decreased over time. The absence of lactic acid is advantageous for hydrogen production, as it does not compete for carbon sources that could otherwise be utilized for synthesizing hydrogen-producing acids such as acetic and butyric acid. Notably, the highest acetone concentration (3.05 g/L) was observed at the conclusion of the fermentation period.

Figure 1. Variation of hydrogen production and total sugar formation from fig waste at 10 g/L concentration

Increasing the fig concentration to 15 g/L resulted in a cumulative hydrogen volume of approximately 25 mL, which is relatively low considering this sugar concentration (Figure 2). The hydrogen production rate was measured at 52.04 mL/L·day. Analysis of the sugar profile showed a general decrease in sugar levels as fermentation progressed. As observed previously, the predominant organic acids were acetic and butyric acids (Table 1). Acetic acid concentration reached 3.41 g/L by the end of fermentation, while butyric acid concentrations remained comparable to those observed with a fig concentration of 10 g/L. The yield of hydrogen gas is notably higher when the predominant end product is acetic acid; lower acetic acid concentrations correspond to reduced hydrogen volumes. Additionally, acetone (1.75 - 2.44 g/L) and ethanol (0.36 - 0.52 g/L) were also detected in the fermentation products.

Table 1. Organic acids and solvents from fig waste at different concentrations

Time (h)	Acetic acid g/L	Butyric acid g/L	Propionic acid g/L	Acetone g/L	Ethanol g/L
10g Fig /L					
0	0.96	1.78	nd	nd	nd
24	1.36	0.63	nd	0.98	0.00
48	2.10	1.13	nd	1.31	0.10
72	2.93	1.27	0.12	1.23	0.00
96	3.23	1.22	0.15	3.05	0.20
15g Fig /L					
0	0.91	1.63	nd	nd	nd
24	1.48	0.85	nd	1.75	0.50
48	2.29	1.12	nd	2.00	0.36
72	3.04	1.28	0.10	1.79	0.46
96	3.41	1.26	0.13	2.44	0.52
20g Fig /L					
0	1.00	0.69	nd	nd	nd
24	1.43	0.80	nd	1.27	0.22
48	2.65	0.91	nd	1.88	nd
72	3.40	1.30	0.10	1.93	0.45
96	3.77	1.29	0.11	1.63	0.78
25g Fig /L					
0	1.02	0.34	nd	nd	nd
24	1.48	1.16	nd	2.08	0.31
48	2.12	1.33	nd	2.04	0.59
72	2.75	1.50	nd	1.25	0.45
96	3.27	1.38	0.07	2.41	0.34
Acetic acid from methane production experiment					
0	1.50	-	-	-	-
24	1.52	-	-	-	-
51	2.02	-	-	-	-
75	2.78	-	-	-	-
147	3.09	-	-	-	-
310	0.18	-	-	-	-
358	0.20	-	-	-	-
478	0.00	-	-	-	-

nd – not detected

Increasing the fig concentration to 20 g/L did not result in a significant enhancement of hydrogen production compared to the 10 g/L concentration. A marginal increase was observed, with hydrogen production reaching 28 mL (Figure 3), and the corresponding hydrogen production rate was 35 mL/L·day. Analysis of the sugar profile indicated an initial decrease in total sugar concentration from 14.27 g/L to approximately 10 g/L at 24- and 48-hours after the start fermentation, suggesting microbial sugar consumption. Subsequently, the sugar concentration increased to 14.46 g/L by the 72nd hour, indicative of partial microbial hydrolysis. By the end of fermentation, a concentration of 9.20 g/L was determined. As in previous experiments, the predominant organic acids were acetic acid (1.00 - 3.77 g/L) and butyric acid (0.69 - 1.30 g/L) (Table 1), with their concentrations increasing as fermentation progressed. Trace amounts of propionic acid were detected. Notably, higher hydrogen gas yields are associated with acetic acid as the primary end product. Additionally, acetone (1.27 - 1.93 g/L) and ethanol (0.22 - 0.78 g/L) were detected in the fermentation products.

Figure 2. Variation of hydrogen production and total sugar formation from fig waste at 15 g/L concentration

Figure 3. Variation of hydrogen production and total sugar formation from fig waste at 20 g/L concentration

Figure 4. Variation of hydrogen production and total sugar formation from fig waste at 25 g/L concentration

Increasing the fig concentration to 25 g/L did not lead to a significant improvement in hydrogen production; instead, a decrease was observed compared to other fig concentrations. This decrease may

be attributed to potential gas leaks during hydrogen volume measurement, with the highest recorded hydrogen volume being 14 mL (Figure 4). Alternatively, substrate inhibition could have contributed to the reduced hydrogen gas production. The declining total sugar concentration over time, without evidence of microbial hydrolysis, along with a high sugar concentration in the liquid phase, suggests substrate inhibition. Analysis of organic acids and solvents (Table 1) in this experimental setup revealed concentrations of acetic acid (1.02 - 3.27 g/L), butyric acid (0.34 - 1.50 g/L), acetone (1.25 - 2.41 g/L), and ethanol (0.31 - 0.59 g/L).

Methane Production Under Mesophilic Conditions

In studies of methane production under mesophilic conditions, residual acetic acid from hydrogen production was used to adjust three different initial total acetic acid concentrations. Methane production was only observed at an initial concentration of 1.50 g/L, indicating challenges for methanogenic bacteria adaptation to the environment. No methane production was detected during the first 75 hours of the experiment. Subsequently, methane production volumes were recorded at 14 mL by the 147th hour, 128 mL by the 310th hour, 163 mL by the 358th hour, and 174 mL by the 478th hour (Figure 5). During this period, the concentration of acetic acid increased from an initial 1.50 g/L to 3.09 g/L by the 147th hour (Table 1). Consumption of acetic acid commenced immediately after the 147th hour and continued to decrease as fermentation progressed, ultimately being fully consumed by the 478th hour. The initiation of acetic acid consumption corresponded with the onset of methane production, affirming that methanogenic bacteria converted acetic acid into methane.

Figure 5. Cumulative methane volume over time at 1.5 g/L initial acetic acid concentration

Conclusion

In this study, partial hydrolysis through thermal treatment successfully released sugars, and bacterial hydrolysis during fermentation transferred residual sugars to the liquid phase. The highest hydrogen production rate of 110.50 mL/L·day were achieved at 10 g/L fig biomass concentration. Acetic and butyric acids were the dominant organic acids determined in all the experimental setup and their concentration increases as fermentation time progress. A relative amount of acetone was also determined in all the experimental setup. As for methane volume, approximately 174 mL was obtained at an initial acetic acid concentration of 1.5 g/L. This is a high volume for a batch reactor. However, the fact that 60% methane was obtained even under batch conditions indicates the process's efficiency. Although the long adaptation period before methane production started appears to be a limitation for the process, this issue can be overcome with continuously operated bioprocesses. The results of this study demonstrate that sugar-rich *Ficus carica* fruit wastes can be converted into renewable energy sources such as biohydrogen, methane, and biohythane using biological agents as a green method.

Acknowledgement

We would like to express our gratitude to the coordination unit of the scientific research projects at Dokuz Eylül University for their support within the scope of project number FLO-2023-3125.

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